

A STUDY OF THE 2-D INTERACTIONS BETWEEN ARBITRARILY ORIENTATED CRACKS AND INCLUSIONS

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ABSTRACT

A model has been developed to predict the 2-D interactions between arbitrarily oriented cracks and inclusions within an infinite matrix. The principle behind the model is the body force method. The solution procedure involves replacement of inclusions and cracks by material of the matrix, creating a homogeneous medium, and on the boundaries application of concentrated point forces and couples respectively. The model is proven for isolated arrangements of cracks and inclusions by comparison with analytical and finite element techniques. Predictions of the interactions between inclusions and cracks are presented and estimates of crack propagation are discussed.

Keywords: body force, crack, fracture mechanics, inclusions, interaction, fibre

1. INTRODUCTION

The failure mechanism of many composite structures involves matrix cracking and subsequent crack propagation. For example, the failure mode of filament wound pipes under cyclic internal pressure loading is weepage. Weepage is the result of many internal matrix cracks linking together to form a convoluted path through the pipe wall. Although this failure mode can be described qualitatively, it cannot be described quantitatively.

The purpose of this paper is to introduce the first stage development of a general model to predict crack propagation, under general far field loads, within fibre reinforced materials using the body force method. This method is considered to handle arrays of cracks and inclusions more efficiently and is more effective than finite elements, particularly so for crack propagation. The mathematical technique describing 2-D interactions between arbitrarily oriented cracks and inclusions (fibres) within an infinite matrix is described. This interaction is defined by fracture mechanics parameters, mode I and II stress intensity factors and from these, crack propagation parameters, extension and direction are deduced.

2. THE BODY FORCE METHOD

The body force method for solving two dimensional crack and inclusion problems is based on using the stress field for a point source in an infinite medium. Inclusions are modelled by

replacing the fibre with matrix material and applying body forces (continuously distributed point forces) at the boundary between the inclusion and matrix, (ref.1). Cracks are modelled by replacing the crack with a distribution of symmetric and anti-symmetric couples, (ref.2). These couples are derived from continuously distributed pairs of point forces spaced infinitesimal distances apart. In calculating the body forces distribution the principle of superposition is implicitly assumed. By replacing the inclusions and cracks by matrix material, an equivalent homogeneous medium is created, (ref.3). This enables contributions from the total distribution of body forces to be added together to satisfy the relevant boundary conditions, (ref.4). This summing enables the interactions between cracks and inclusions to be calculated efficiently.

For 2-D problems the components of stress from the body force density distribution are expressed in terms of complex potentials, $\phi(z)$ and $\Gamma(z)$, (ref.5);

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_y + \sigma_x &= 2(\phi'(z) + \overline{\phi'(z)}) \\ \sigma_y - \sigma_x + 2i\tau_{xy} &= 2(\overline{z}\phi''(z) + \Gamma'(z))\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where ' represents differentiation with respect to z .

3. INCLUSIONS

For a concentrated point force, $X+iY$, acting at an arbitrary point, z_0 , within an infinite medium, complex potentials, $\phi(z)$ and $\Gamma(z)$, are, (ref.5);

$$\phi(z) = -(X+iY) \text{Log}(z-z_0) / 2\pi(1+\beta) \quad (2)$$

$$\Gamma(z) = \{ \beta(X-iY) \text{Log}(z-z_0) + \overline{z_0}(X+iY) / (z-z_0) \} / 2\pi(1+\beta)$$

For plane strain, $\beta = 3-4\mu$, whereas for plane stress, $\beta = (3-\mu)/(1+\mu)$. μ is the Poisson ratio. The inclusion is replaced by matrix material with body forces, continuously distributed point forces, applied along the imaginary boundary. The magnitude of these body forces is calculated by relating the resulting stresses to the boundary conditions which are deduced from the stress deficit caused by replacing the inclusion with matrix material. For a single inclusion, the imaginary boundary is divided into m equal segments, where within each segment, j , the body force densities, N_j and T_j , are constant. The normal and tangential stresses at z , due to segment j is;

$$(\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_j = \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \{ \phi'(z) + \overline{\phi'(z)} - \exp(2i\theta_0)(\overline{z}\phi''(z) + \Gamma'(z)) \} dz_0 \quad (3)$$

The $2m$ unknown body force densities are determined by calculating the stresses at the midpoint of every j th segment due to the total body force density distribution and equating them to the normal and tangential stress boundary conditions. The normal and tangential stresses at the midpoint of segment k due to the complete body force density distribution is;

$$(\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_k = \sum_{j=1}^m (\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_j + (\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_\infty \quad (4)$$

Replacing the inclusion by matrix material results in a stress deficit;

$$\delta \underline{\sigma}_k = (\underline{Q}_{kj}^f - \underline{Q}_{kj}^m) \underline{S}_{kj}^f \underline{\sigma}_k \quad (5)$$

Transforming Cartesian stresses to polar; $\underline{\sigma}_k = \underline{T}^{-1} \underline{\sigma}_{rk}$, where \underline{T}^{-1} represents matrix inversion, the normal and tangential boundary conditions at the midpoint of segment k are;

$$(\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_k = \underline{T} (\underline{Q}_{kj}^f - \underline{Q}_{kj}^m) \underline{S}_{kj}^f \underline{T}^{-1} (N_k - iT_k) \quad (6)$$

Equating equation (4) to (6) provides the 2m equations required to solve for, $N_k - iT_k$;

$$(\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_\infty = \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\sum_{j=1}^m -(\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_j + \underline{T} (\underline{Q}_{kj}^f - \underline{Q}_{kj}^m) \underline{S}_{kj}^f \underline{T}^{-1} (N_k - iT_k) \right] \quad (7)$$

For multiple inclusions, the stresses, $(\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_{k,l}$, at the midpoint of the k th segment of the l th inclusion, are determined by extending equation (4) to include contributions from body forces distributed along the boundaries of the other (n-1) inclusions. Figure 1 provides a comparison between body force predictions and finite element stress calculations for three diametrically similar inclusions under uni-axial tension (y-direction). The ratio of inclusion to matrix Young's modulus is 21.14. Each inclusion is divided into 32 segments. The parallel and perpendicular stresses to the applied stress are compared along the x-axis from the edge of the centre inclusion to a distance of 0.5 diameters. The agreement between the two calculation procedures is excellent.

Figure 1. Comparison between body force and F.E. predictions for three inclusions.

4. CRACKS

The complex potentials, $\phi(z)$ and $\Gamma(z)$, for a symmetric and anti-symmetric couple, R and S, are;

$$\begin{aligned}\phi(z) &= -\left\{2(\beta-1)/(1+\beta) R - iS\right\} \exp(2i\alpha)/(z-z_0)/2\pi(1+\beta) \\ \Gamma(z) &= -\left\{4(\beta-1)/(1+\beta)R/(z-z_0) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left[2(\beta-1)/(1+\beta)R - iS\right]\bar{z}_0 \exp(2i\alpha)/(z-z_0)^2\right\}/2\pi(1+\beta)\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

The crack is replaced by matrix material with body force couples applied along the crack length. The magnitude of the couples is determined by equating the resulting stresses to the boundary conditions at the imaginary crack boundary.

The stresses at a particular point z, due to distributed couples along a crack, length 2a, are;

$$\sigma_y - i\tau_{xy} = \int_{-a}^a \left\{ \phi'(z) + \overline{\phi'(z)} + \bar{z}\phi''(z) + \Gamma'(z) \right\} dz_0 \quad (9)$$

Along the crack face these stresses are;

$$(\sigma_y - i\tau_{xy})_c = \int_{-a}^a \left\{ [R' - iS'] \exp(2i\alpha)/(z-z_0)^2 \right\} / \pi dz_0 \quad (10)$$

where $R' = R 2(\beta-1)/(1+\beta)^2$ and $S' = S/(1+\beta)$. These stresses must cancel the uniform stresses (far field stresses) in the "uncracked" plate to satisfy the crack face boundary conditions. A weighting function is introduced into the definition of R' and S';

$$R' - iS' = (R'' - iS'')F(z_0) \text{ where } F(z_0) = (a^2 - z_0^2)^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

and integrating over the crack length, implies; $(\sigma_y - i\tau_{xy})_c = -(R'' - iS'')$ (12)

The weighted body force couple distribution is uniform along the crack face and satisfying the boundary conditions along the crack face implies; $R'' - iS'' = (\sigma_y - i\tau_{xy})_\infty$ (13)

The behaviour of the stress field as the crack tip is approached can be shown to be;

$$(\sigma_y - i\tau_{xy})_s = (\sigma_y - i\tau_{xy})_\infty (a/2r)^{1/2} = (K_I - iK_{II}) / (2\pi r)^{1/2} \quad (14)$$

where K_I and K_{II} are the mode I and II stress intensity factors and r is the distance from the crack tip..

For multiple cracks the weighted body force couple distributions vary according to the respective crack positions. The imaginary crack boundaries are divided into m equal segments where within each segment, j , the couple densities, R_j and S_j , are constant. The normal and tangential stresses at z , due to segment j are;

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\sigma_y - i\tau_{xy})_j = \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \{ & [R''_j - iS''_j] \exp(2i\alpha)/(z - z_o)^2 + [R''_j + iS''_j] \exp(-2i\alpha)/(z - z_o)^2 + \\
 & 4R''_j/(z - z_o)^2 + 2[R''_j - iS''_j] \exp(2i\alpha)(\bar{z} - \bar{z}_o)/(z - z_o)^3 \} (a^2 - z_o^2)^{1/2} / 2\pi dz_o
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{15}$$

There are $2mn$ unknown couple densities, n is the number of cracks, assuming each crack is divided into m segments, are determined by calculating the stresses at the midpoint of every j th segment due to the total couple density distribution and equating them to the boundary conditions. These stresses are;

$$\sum_{p=1}^m \sum_{q=1}^n [(\sigma_x - i\tau_{xy})_{\infty}] = \sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{l=1}^n -(\sigma_x - i\tau_{xy})_{k,l} \tag{16}$$

To improve the accuracy of the procedure, instead of assuming a constant profile of body forces within a segment, a linear profile can be used. A further improvement to the accuracy is to consider the forces acting over the crack length rather than the stresses, (ref.2). This implies that the new boundary conditions require the resultant of the stresses exerted on each interval by the applied body force couples to compensate the stresses induced in the "uncracked" plate.

The stress intensity factor at the l th crack tip are given by;

$$(K_I - iK_{II})_l = (R'' - iS'')_l (\pi a)^{1/2} \tag{17}$$

Figure 2. Normalised S.I.F.'s for approaching cracks of length $2a$ under uni-axial tension.

Figure 2 presents the inner and outer normalised mode I SIF's for two equal length approaching cracks under uni-axial tension (y-direction). Each crack is divided into 32 segments. As the cracks approach the inner K value tends to infinity, the outer to 1.414, the normalised SIF for a single double length crack.

5. INTERACTIONS BETWEEN CRACKS AND INCLUSIONS

For interactions between multiple inclusions and cracks the solutions outlined in the previous sections are combined. The boundaries of the p cracks and q inclusions are each divided into m segments and n arcs respectively. In total there are 2(mp+nq) unknowns. The stresses resulting from the total body force distributions on both cracks and inclusions are equated to the inclusion boundary conditions at the 2nq arc midpoints, i.e. the sum of equations (7) and (16);

$$\sum_{t=1}^q \sum_{s=1}^n [(\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_\infty = -\sum_{h=1}^q \sum_{j=1}^n (\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_{j,h} + \{ \underline{T}(\underline{Q}_{kj}^f - \underline{Q}_{kj}^m) \underline{S}_{kj}^f \underline{T}^{-1} \} (N_{k,l} - iT_{k,l}) - \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^m (\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_{k,l}] \tag{18}$$

Also, the stresses are equated to the crack boundary conditions at the 2mp segment mid-points, i.e. equations (4) and (16);

$$\sum_{t=1}^q \sum_{s=1}^n [(\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_\infty = -\sum_{h=1}^q \sum_{j=1}^n (\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_{j,h} - \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^m (\sigma_r - i\tau_\theta)_{k,l}] \tag{19}$$

Figure 3. Normalised S.I.F.'s for a crack near an inclusion against separation distance.

Summing equations (18) and (19) provides the $2(mp+nq)$ equations to satisfy the boundary conditions. Figure 3 presents body force predictions for mode I normalised stress intensity factors (SIF's) for a single crack interacting with a single inclusion against lateral separation distance under uni-axial tension (y -direction). The inclusion is divided into 32 arcs and the crack into 20 segments. The ratio of inclusion to matrix Young's modulus is 10. Also plotted in Figure 3 are predictions from Erdogan et.al., (ref.6). The agreement is excellent. As the crack approaches the inclusion, both mode I crack tip SIF's decrease from the far field value of unity. The SIF for crack tip A, appears to be tending to zero.

6. CRACK PROPAGATION

Crack propagation in brittle materials generally involves a sudden break within the material with little deformation prior to fracture. In polymeric thermosetting composites such brittle fractures are usually contained between fibres. Subsequent crack extension may then be stable via a fatigue mechanism. To predict fatigue crack propagation, three parameters are required; a fracture initiation value, an angle and magnitude of crack extension.

To predict fracture initiation after fatigue crack growth and crack extension angle, the strain energy density criterion developed by Sih, (ref.7), is used;

$$S = a_{11}K_I^2 + 2a_{12}K_I K_{II} + a_{22}K_{II}^2 \quad (20)$$

$$\text{where } a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{22} = f(\beta, \phi, G) \quad (\text{see (ref.7)})$$

and ϕ is the angle with respect to in-plane crack co-ordinates, G is the shear modulus. To estimate crack extension during fatigue a simplified relation between crack extension and mode I SIF is used; $\delta a = A K_I^2$ (21)

It is assumed that both mode I and II SIFs remain constant during crack extension. This assumption limits the magnitude of extension, especially when the crack is propagating through a rapidly varying stress field.

Figure 4. Crack propagation path for a crack near 2 symmetrical inclusions (fibres).

Figure 4 presents the crack propagation path for a crack, length $2a$, interacting with two symmetrically positioned fibres under uni-axial tension. Only half the diagram is shown. The ratio of fibre to matrix Young's modulus is 21.14. Both the inclusion and crack are divided into 32 segments. The crack propagation path is built up of individual cracks linked together, with the length of each new crack set to the calculated crack extension. Each crack extension is divided into 6 segments. The constant A , in Equation (21) is chosen as 0.05. For the first few steps, the crack propagates towards the inclusion with the mode I SIF increasing, resulting in larger crack extensions with little variation in crack extension angle. For the next steps the SIF reduces implying smaller crack extensions, again with little variation in crack extension angle. In the final few steps there is a dramatic increase in crack extension angle, deflecting the crack from the inclusion interface due to the rapidly increasing mode II SIF. It is implicitly assumed in this example that the fibre/matrix interface is perfectly bonded.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The body force method has been applied to problems where cracks and inclusions interact. The method, although requiring numerical computations is simple to formulate and relatively benign on computational time.

For inclusions, the body force method is compared with finite element predictions and the difference between the two predictive techniques is negligible. For isolated cracks, the correct order of the crack tip singularity is analytically demonstrated. For interacting cracks, approaching each other, the numerical solution asymptotes to the correct solution for a double length crack. For a single crack interacting with a single inclusion, results are compared with an analytical solution of elliptic integrals, again with negligible differences.

To estimate crack propagation, the strain energy density criterion along with a simplified Paris type law for crack extension is used. For a single crack propagating towards an inclusion (of greater modulus than the matrix) it is demonstrated that the inclusion acts as a crack deflector.

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